

Greek epigraphy in Sicily, 2017-2021

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Abstract: This paper offers a survey of newly published and significantly revised Greek inscriptions, and other relevant publications, from the island of Sicily over the five years 2017-2021. The survey focuses on epigraphy on stone and metal. Particular attention is drawn to the development of the digital corpus, *I.Sicily*, to the expansion of materials in the indigenous languages of Sikel and Elymian, to study of material from Segesta, Halaesa, Messina and Himera, to *defixiones* and other metal epigraphy, to new funerary inscriptions, and to material and studies relevant to *sigla*, onomastics, numerals, institutions, and socio-linguistics.

Keywords: Greek epigraphy, Ancient Sicily, *defixiones*, epitaphs, onomastics, socio-linguistics

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A survey of Greek epigraphy in Sicily for the period 2017-2021 should begin by acknowledging the end of an era for the subject, with the death, in December 2016, of Giacomo Manganaro. There is scarcely a Sicilian inscription which has not been touched by him at some point, and he stands alongside Paolo Orsi for the sheer volume of epigraphic material that he published. The study of the epigraphy and history of the island will always be indebted to him.¹

Indeed, the last of the traditional quinquennial surveys for Greek epigraphy appearing in this journal was undertaken by Giacomo Manganaro himself in 2001, explicitly reduced in ambition from the preceding magisterial surveys of Antonietta Brugnone.² The renewal of the ambition of providing such surveys is to be welcomed, even if the task is an invidious one. I shall focus on new material, significant revisions, and thematic studies that are primarily epigraphic in their frame, in the hope that this will be of use to those interested in either epigraphy or ancient Sicily.³ Those working directly in the field will inevitably spot omissions – and the author begs that these be understood as entirely accidental.

One of the greatest challenges for those studying Sicily – or indeed many other regions – is to find out about newly studied or published material. The annual bulletins/gazetteers of *SEG* and *BE* in theory serve to meet that need, and the immense effort that goes into such works should be

¹ For Manganaro's complete bibliography, see RIZZONE 2016 (*I.Sicily* currently references material from 97 separate publications by Manganaro).

² MANGANARO 2008 (but a paper of 2001); cf. BRUGNONE 1997-1998. GULLETTA 1999 provides a wide-ranging set of surveys of Sicilian epigraphy; cf. TRIBULATO 2012 for a heavily epigraphic set of linguistic surveys.

³ Inscriptions on ceramic and *instrumentum* will only be mentioned incidentally.

acknowledged: Anna Magonetto has taken over from Laurent Dubois in covering Sicily for the *Bulletin Épigraphique*, while Eftychia Stavrianopoulou edits the Sicilian section of *Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum*. But as the proliferation of publication (although not necessarily new material) continues to grow apace, such a task becomes ever more difficult: at the time of final editing of this paper, *SEG* was still only up to 2018 (one should perhaps note that the ever longer summaries of publications that *SEG* provides, rather than the original plain reports of texts and revisions, must contribute to this delay and the increasing size of the volumes, and the viability of the project in this form must surely be questioned); by the time of submission, *BE* will have reached 2023, although it is more selective. In this context, a pair of new initiatives should be noted, and inserted alongside the traditional appeals of *BE* and *SEG* to be sent notices of epigraphic publications: '*Officina di IG XIV*²', and '*I.Sicily*'. The former project, led by Roberta Fabiani and Giulio Vallarino, launched online in 2022 and aims to provide a focal point for the work commissioned by the Berlin Brandenburg Academy (BBAW) to produce a second edition of *Inscriptiones Graecae XIV*.⁴ The first edition of *IG XIV*, by Georg Kaibel, intended to cover the Greek inscriptions of the West (*Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus*), was published in 1890, and revision is sorely needed. *Officina* organises seminars, maintains news of work and recent publications, and supports the publication of new material through the Venice-based online journal for Greek epigraphy, *Axon*, directed by Stefania De Vido.⁵ *I.Sicily* (see below) was launched in 2017 with the aim of providing full coverage of Sicilian epigraphy, and partners BBAW and *Officina* in the work of producing the revision of the Sicilian section of *IG XIV* (for which Jonathan Prag currently has responsibility).⁶ *Officina* and *I.Sicily* aim to provide reasonably up-to-date bibliography for epigraphic publications for Magna Graecia and Sicily respectively, and readers are warmly encouraged to send any news or details of publications to the relevant project.⁷ New Sicilian inscriptions are incorporated directly into *I.Sicily* as soon as is practical.

With the ambition of comprehensiveness and accessibility to researcher in mind, this survey begins therefore not with an inscription but with an overview of *I.Sicily*. The *I.Sicily* project formally went live at the beginning of 2017.⁸ The project, hosted by the University of Oxford and directed by Jonathan Prag, aims to maintain a comprehensive and open access digital corpus of all the inscriptions from ancient Sicily, through to at least the 7th century CE.⁹ The project is actively supported by the Assessorato regionale dei beni culturali e dell'identità siciliana, under the terms of a convention signed in January 2022; and the content continues to be expanded and developed as part of the ERC-funded, five-year *Crossreads* project (2020-2025) on the epigraphic culture of the island.¹⁰

⁴ <https://www.officina-igxiv2.org/home-page> (accessed 02.04.2024).

⁵ <https://edizionicafoscari.unive.it/v4/it/edizioni4/riviste/axon/> (accessed 02.04.2024).

⁶ <https://isicily.org/> and <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/> (accessed 02.04.2024).

⁷ For Magna Graecia, see <https://www.officina-igxiv2.org/magna-graecia-epigraphica> (accessed 02.04.2024), curated by Teresa Sissy De Blasio; for Sicily, <https://isicily.org/home/news/> (accessed 02.04.2024).

⁸ The same year saw the publication of *Italia Epigrafica Digitale, volume IX, Sicilia* by the Epigraphic Database Roma, a version of record, publishing in PDF the 2,034 Sicilian records at that point included in EDR (BRUGNONE, MOTTA 2017).

⁹ On *I.Sicily* see PRAG, CHARTRAND 2018 and PRAG 2019; on the recent expansion through *Crossreads*, see PRAG 2021a and (in Italian) PRAG, SOMMERSCHIEDL 2021.

¹⁰ *Crossreads* has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme Grant agreement No. 885040; this paper has been completed with the support of that project.

As a fully digital corpus, in which inscriptions are continuously revised and updated, and as a project based upon extensive work of autopsy and cataloguing, it might be hoped that it would be possible to extract data on newly published or revised inscriptions for a specific period or language directly and automatically from the corpus. Such an ideal remains an ambition, rather than a reality, albeit a plausible and realistic ambition for the future: individual records contain details of revision, but these cannot yet be systematically searched. It is however already possible to search detailed bibliography for the epigraphy of the island.¹¹ Nonetheless, the corpus provides an increasingly comprehensive reference point, which, hopefully makes the reference to and study of Sicilian inscriptions increasingly easy, in both Ancient Greek and other languages. *I.Sicily* inscriptions take the form ISic123456, and resolve as URLs of the form: <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic123456>; records contain detailed bibliography as well as cross-references to other digital corpora, so that in principle an ISic reference should be sufficient, unless a particular published edition is under discussion, and they will be used throughout this paper (*I.Sicily* references are also aligned with Trismegistos numbers). It should also be noted that *I.Sicily* editions, while based upon published editions in the first instance, are steadily being updated with new editions based upon fresh autopsy and re-study.

I.Sicily currently (January 2024) publishes 4695 inscriptions from the island.¹² In 2017 there were 3205 inscriptions, and by early 2021 the corpus had only increased to 3306, reflecting the fact that the major work of expansion and updating of the online corpus post-dates the pandemic. We expect the current total to increase by approximately a further 1,000 in the coming year, reflecting the final incorporation of mostly later Roman and early Christian material from Catania and Siracusa (the majority of which is in Greek). Although preliminary editions are based upon published work, the emphasis is upon the systematic restudy, cataloguing, and photographing of the material; and the format is not that of a database, but of a full edition for each inscription. Individual editions are additionally subject to ongoing revision. As supported by the Assessorato, the ambition is to collaborate with every museum, archaeological park and soprintendenza on the island, to enable the systematic restudy and improved accessibility of all the epigraphic material on the island, for both researchers and the general public. Emblematic is the long-term collaboration with the Museo archeologico regionale Paolo Orsi di Siracusa, and the Parco archeologico di Siracusa. This collaboration began formally in 2014, and is now the subject of a new collaboration agreement, signed in January 2022. At the museum, we have so far catalogued and photographed over 1,000 inscriptions (many fragmentary, many unpublished), and identified approximately 1,300 in the inventory (but not all those we have catalogued are in the inventory, and some of those in the inventory are now in the PCAS antiquarium of the catacombs, so the final total will not be 1,300, but rather more). Many of these will be added to the site and published in the coming year, and include previously unpublished archaic, Hellenistic and Roman material. A major part of the Syracuse project is the work to catalogue and publish the complete set of inscriptions from the Siracusa catacombs, in collaboration with both the museum and the PCAS, as a parallel project to the production of *Inscriptiones Christianae Italiae: Siracusa* – formal collaboration was agreed in 2018, and, after the tragic death of Mariarita Sgarlata in 2019, another great loss to the epigraphic community, the project is now being led by Ilenia Gradante and Maria Domenica Lo Faro.¹³ Most of the substantive

¹¹ See <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/publications> (accessed 02.04.2024) or the underlying Zotero library at: <https://www.zotero.org/groups/382445/isicily/library> (accessed 02.04.2024).

¹² Archival copies of the EpiDoc XML files are stored in Zenodo, under the DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2556743.

¹³ See now GRADANTE, MANENTI, PRAG 2023.

advances in *I.Sicily*, as part of the *Crossreads* project, post-date the period covered by this survey and so will not be detailed here. Two areas do however deserve highlighting.

Firstly, the process of collaboration is not limited to the simple ambition of incorporating the material into the online corpus of *I.Sicily*. The project is also focused on supporting dissemination and education. A major collaboration with Daria Spampinato of the ISTC-CNR in Catania, the Museo Civico di Catania (and the then Assessore di Cultura for Catania, Orazio Licandro) and the Liceo artistico “M.M. Lazzaro” of Catania, resulted in both a digital catalogue of the museum’s inscriptions and a new exhibition of a selection of 35 of the museum’s inscriptions, which opened on 14 July 2017.¹⁴ At Halaesa, collaboration with the Soprintendenza di Messina (Gabriella Tigano, Rocco Burgio) and the Parco archeologico di Tindari enabled the creation of a new lapidarium displaying most of the inscriptions from the site, together with a new catalogue.¹⁵ Just before the period of this survey, collaboration with Gioconda Lamagna, Angela Merendina and the Parco archeologico di Catania resulted in a new catalogue of the epigraphic collection of the Museo regionale Saro Franco di Adrano.¹⁶ Preliminary trials in the use of digital resources to expand the accessibility of inscriptions have led to the use of QR codes at the Museo archeologico regionale “Paolo Orsi”, in Siracusa. It should also be emphasised that all Sicilian museums already have a digital catalogue of the epigraphic collection available online through the *I.Sicily* interface.¹⁷ Work on individual collections provides an ideal opportunity to help in the development of epigraphic skills. A number of university students have collaborated in the work of cataloguing at the Museo archeologico regionale “Paolo Orsi”, in Siracusa (notably Flavio Santini), while students of several local Licei undertook work on epigraphic materials and display at the museum; students of the Liceo artistico “M.M. Lazzaro” of Catania participated in the work of cataloguing and exhibition creation at the Museo Civico di Catania; and we held the first of several planned training workshops for students of Palermo University at the Museo archeologico regionale “A.Salinas”, Palermo and the University of Palermo in May 2022.

Secondly, a brief survey is warranted of recent work on the Elymian and Sikel epigraphy of the island both within *I.Sicily* and beyond, since this is of interest not least for its direct relevance to and interaction with the use of Greek on the island, and the island’s Greek epigraphic culture. The most significant event in the context of the indigenous languages of ancient Sicily was undoubtedly the long-awaited publication in 2020 of Luciano Agostiniani’s supplement to his original corpus of the Elymian texts, presenting another 73 inscriptions in addition to the 371 previously published in the 1977 corpus.¹⁸ Sadly Luciano Agostiniani passed away in 2022, another serious loss to the study of Sicilian epigraphy. A collection of the Sikel material was in preparation and it is to be hoped that it will still be brought through to publication: several elements of that work have already been published, including a late sixth- or early fifth-century BCE funerary inscription on a limestone slab from Ragusa Ibla (found in 2010 in contrada Rose), which Agostiniani argues to be in Greek but showing significant contact with the local Sikel language.¹⁹ In parallel to the work of Agostiniani, through the efforts of Valentina Mignosa in 2021, all 444 Elymian texts are now included in *I.Sicily*, and in collaboration with the Museo Archeologico Regionale Salinas di Palermo some 360 of these

¹⁴ See AGODI et al. 2018 for a description of the project.

¹⁵ PRAG, TIGANO 2017.

¹⁶ PRAG 2015.

¹⁷ <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/museums> (accessed 02.04.2024).

¹⁸ AGOSTINIANI 2021; cf. AGOSTINIANI 1977.

¹⁹ AGOSTINIANI, SCERRA 2017 (ISic004498), cf. SCERRA 2018; note also AGOSTINIANI 2017, a *kylix* from Sabucina bearing a Sikel text, not in fact an *ineditum*, but already published as R. ARENA 2002, no.103 (ISic020563).

have been photographed for inclusion in colour, at high resolution. Mignosa has additionally united 181 nominally Sikel texts in *I.Sicily*, the autopsy of which is underway. A major challenge with the indigenous material involves the difficulty of identifying whether a text is actually in Greek, Sikel, or Elymian, especially given the material's frequently fragmentary nature. It is our hope that the incorporation of all the material together in *I.Sicily*, whether Elymian, Greek, or Sikel will greatly facilitate future study, not least because digital encoding avoids the necessity of binary classification, allowing material to be considered more flexibly. Such study will be supported in due course by the detailed analysis of both palaeography and linguistics in the *I.Sicily* corpus as part of the *Crossreads* project. Recent work, particularly by Agostiniani, Mignosa, and Olga Tribulato has increasingly focused upon the socio-linguistics as well as more systematic study of linguistic and palaeographic features in order to enrich our understanding of this key area of cultural interaction on the island in the archaic period: the recently analysed material from the necropolis at Montagna di Marzo and the new *abecedarium* from Manico di Quarara are emblematic of this work.²⁰

Similar approaches are increasingly enriching study of the more limited Oscan corpus from ancient Messina. Here the work in particular of both Katherine McDonald and Nicholas Zair, integrating the Messina material into wider studies of Oscan as a whole, facilitated in turn by the corpus-building work of Crawford's *Imagines Italicae*, means that the combination of socio-linguistic approaches and greater contextualisation have led to much more nuanced interpretation of the material.²¹ The interaction between Greek and Oscan at Messina is further enriched by the new material published by Emiliano Arena, discussed below.

Turning fully to the Greek epigraphy of the period 2017-2021, four urban sites in particular have seen substantial activity: Segesta, Halaesa, Messina and Himera. Probably the single most significant epigraphic publication on paper in this period is the corpus of Segestan inscriptions, published in 2019 by Carmine Ampolo and Donnatella Erdas. The volume is an exemplary and comprehensive analysis and presentation of the corpus of the Segestan material, with full archaeological contexts, reflecting c.30 years of work on the site by the Scuola Normale di Pisa.²² In addition to the 34 Greek and 20 Latin texts presented (several of the numbered entries in fact contain multiple texts), a series of appendices present important texts from elsewhere which reference Segesta (the treaty with Athens, decrees of Nakone and Entella, the dedication by a Segestan at Erice, and the inscription of the Roman consul Gaius Duilius).²³ The introductory material includes an invaluable discussion of palaeography and linguistics by Donnatella Erdas, capitalising on the supporting archaeological evidence, which places much of the material in the later second and first centuries BCE. The presence of rhomboid characters, especially omicron is singled out, which increasingly looks to be a notable Sicilian feature in the western Mediterranean, visible already in the second century BCE.²⁴ The previously unpublished material includes four new Hellenistic statue base inscriptions: three

²⁰ See TRIBULATO 2017 for the *abecedarium* (ISic020442), AGOSTINIANI, ALBANESE PROCELLI 2018 for Montagna di Marzo (also FARIELLO 2020), MIGNOSA 2017 on Mendolito, TRIBULATO, MIGNOSA 2021 for the specific case of the 'Sikel alpha', and PRAG 2020 for a recent survey of the indigenous languages. Note also STANCO et al. 2016 for the 3D laser-scanning of the Mendolito inscription (MARPO inv. 96962 = ISic003364, <https://skfb.ly/6xSGV> (accessed 02.04.2024)) and other Sicilian material by the USF Institute for Digital Exploration, directed by Davide Tanasi.

²¹ Formally just outside the period of this survey, but see McDONALD 2015 and ZAIR 2016, and now ZAIR 2020.

²² AMPOLO, ERDAS 2019; see also AMPOLO, PARRA 2018 for the epigraphy in its archaeological context.

²³ A near complete listing of the material can be found at <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/publication/3PK3JKXR> (accessed 02.04.2024).

²⁴ ERDAS, in AMPOLO, ERDAS 2019, 35-39.

second-century BCE Hellenistic examples of the people honouring members of the local elite, while the fourth is fragmentary but in a style (and with linguistic features) suggesting an honorific of the early Roman imperial period.²⁵ Of considerable importance is the consolidated republication (with revisions) of the series of inscriptions on substantial blocks from the north stoa, the faces of which are carved into rounded *tabulae ansatae*, and which record building works undertaken by the local elite.²⁶ Also previously unpublished are a fragment of an inscribed cornice, probably from a late Hellenistic statue base, probably set up by the ephebes, and a significant corpus of quarry or construction marks recorded across multiple structures on the site.²⁷ The last of these is a category of material which deserves more systematic study and is beginning to attract wider attention in the archaeological and epigraphical community more generally.²⁸ The corpus also includes a number of ceramic graffiti and dipinti of interest from both an economic and a socio-linguistic perspective, and the Segestan material as a whole provides valuable evidence for the linguistic interference between Greek and Latin in the later Hellenistic and early Roman period (see below).

Inevitably, the publication of the corpus was immediately followed by the discovery of two new inscriptions: one, published by Ampolo in 2021, survives as two fragments of what is probably another statue base for a member of the Segestan elite, with the name Phalakros already attested in the theatre inscriptions.²⁹ The piece confirms what the authors of the corpus had already strongly emphasised, namely the prominence of the local civic elite in the life of Segesta and other later Hellenistic urban centres in Sicily. The second, found in 2021 and promptly published by Ampolo, is a remarkable statue base, found *in situ* in a structure immediately below and to the south of the agora.³⁰ The base was set up by Diodoros, son of Tittelos, in honour of his father, in parallel to the previously attested inscription set up by the same man in honour of his sister Minyra, priestess of Aphrodite.³¹ Perhaps most importantly the base attests explicitly to the construction of the *ephebikon* by Diodoros' father, most likely the room in which the base was found, and a new use of this rare adjective, which also confirms the presence and location of the *gymnasion* in Segesta. Graffiti identified on the adjacent wall are currently being studied.

The gymnasia of Hellenistic Sicily have themselves been the focus of increasing work in recent years, with renewed attention from several scholars including Monika Trümper, who has now begun excavation of the *gymnasion* at Agrigento.³² The epigraphic evidence continues to accrue, not only at Segesta.³³ Firstly a fragment found in re-use in the wall of a modern house in Centuripe, recording

²⁵ *I.Segesta* G3 (ISic001679), G4 (ISic001680), G5 (ISic001681), and G6 (ISic001691) (the later one).

²⁶ *I.Segesta* G10-G13 (ISic001111, ISic001112, ISic002939, ISic002938); cf. AMPOLO, ERDAS 2018 for a detailed contextualisation of G12 (ISic002939).

²⁷ *I.Segesta* G24 (ISic004514) for the fragment; 19 quarry marks are united by building under G20-G23.

²⁸ For Sicily, compare Himera examples, briefly referenced in BRUGNONE 2017a, 37.

²⁹ AMPOLO 2021a, numbered as *I.Segesta* G35a-b (ISic001699); cf. *I.Segesta* G7a-b (ISic001107-1108).

³⁰ AMPOLO 2022, numbered as *I.Segesta* G36 (ISic001700).

³¹ *I.Segesta* G1 (ISic001106), now on display in the new, small on-site antiquarium at Segesta.

³² TRÜMPER 2018 and 2019 brings a due note of archaeological caution to the discussion; but I take the opportunity to note, *contra* TRÜMPER 2018, 44 note 2, that PRAG 2007, 93 did *not* 'assume that all 65 cities of Late Republican Sicily provided a gymnasion', but rather briefly entertained what was only ever described as a 'very improbable assumption', solely for the purposes of a demographic hypothetical (which was in turn explicitly described as 'obviously unacceptable' in its raw form). Straw men are very useful, but not if they are fictitious (and depressingly then repeated in SEG 68.717).

³³ Although note that the re-editing of *I.Segesta* G13 (ISic002938) means it almost certainly no longer contains a possible reference to a *gymnasion*; rediscussion of the case of Segesta in CANNISTRACI, OLIVITO 2018 (without the re-reading of G13), and of Solunto in GRECO 2020, in part with reference to *JG* XIV.311 (ISic001130).

a dedication to Hermes and Herakles on the part of one or more gymnasiarchs, probably of the later Hellenistic period.³⁴ Secondly, the impressive remains at Cava d'Ispica, where Vittorio Rizzone and the late Annamaria Sammito have brought to our attention the rupestral gymnasium, identified by the prominent, but also curiously abbreviated wall inscriptions, identifying one of the large rock-cut spaces as being for the νεω(τέροι) and the πρε(σβύτεροι).³⁵ Against this backdrop, note the re-opening of the Museo Civico di Noto, with various inscriptions restored to view, including the important gymnasial dedication recording the *neaniskoi Hieronianoï*, from the gymnasium of ancient Netum.³⁶

The second new civic corpus published in this period is that for Halaesa, produced by myself, together with Gabriella Tigano.³⁷ This partly republishes known material from the site, including lost material in the antiquarian record and inscriptions now in other museums (principally Palermo), but also provides the first publication of a series of new texts, mostly excavated and preliminarily studied by the late Giacomo Scibona.³⁸ The majority of the unpublished material is in Latin (23 texts), but the two new Greek texts are noteworthy. Firstly a fragmentary late Hellenistic dedication to Serapis, adding this divinity, epigraphically attested also at Syracusae and Tauromenium, to the pantheon at Halaesa.³⁹ Secondly, the solitary Greek inscription from the high imperial period at Halaesa, an honorific for a *rhetor*, with a name implying an origin from Roman Africa, one Aelius Asinius Petitus.⁴⁰ At Halaesa the epigraphic culture switches entirely to Latin in the Augustan period, and the text is a rare example of a public honorific in Greek not only at Halaesa but from the island as a whole under the High Empire. Carved in fine letters, with words separated by interpuncts, it provides a nice example of the use of Greek to assert high literary culture within an otherwise Latin-using epigraphic milieu, very familiar from the so-called Second Sophistic and a pattern of practice well attested in southern Italy, but far less visible in Sicily (compare however the new verse dedication to Orion from Messina, below).

The epigraphic gains from Halaesa are however considerably more substantial than these texts alone. The remarkable pair of bronzes, in which a *koinon* of the priests of Apollo honours Nemenios son of Daphnis, found in 2004 and initially published by Scibona in 2009, have now been republished in detail by Prag and also by Anna Maria Prestianni Giallombardo.⁴¹ In addition and relatedly Prestianni Giallombardo has convincingly argued that the monogram, attested in the cadastral

³⁴ The only published notice to my knowledge is online (18 September 2017), in *ArcheoSicilia* by Isabella Di Bartolo (<https://archeosicilia.blogspot.com/2017/09/centuripe-scoperta-la-dedica-di-un.html>), but a record is available as ISic004370 in *I.Sicily*.

³⁵ RIZZONE, SAMMITO 2017, 14-15 with figs. 9-10 (now ISic001864 and ISic001865). The authors give véo(ι) as their primary reading, while noting that νεω(τέροι) would be more likely (the photograph is insufficient to control the reading); Monika TRÜMPER (*per litt.*) reads NEΩ (open rhomboid omega). Further inscriptions are mentioned, including the letters AMΦH, but not interpreted.

³⁶ IG XIV.240 (ISic001060 for images); for the material on display in the museum, see <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/museum/100>.

³⁷ PRAG, TIGANO 2017; for a listing of the material see <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/publication/MI64NB9L>.

³⁸ SCIBONA 2017 (published 2019) is a posthumous publication of the new material prepared by C. GIUFFRÉ, employing preliminary drafts prepared by Prag based in turn upon autopsy and the original transcriptions and notes of G. SCIBONA.

³⁹ ISic003686 (PRAG, TIGANO 2017, no.4), cf. ISic003002 (IG XIV.14a) from Syracusae and ISic001258 (IG XIV.433) from Tauromenium.

⁴⁰ ISic003591 (PRAG, TIGANO 2017, no.28).

⁴¹ ISic030277 and ISic030278: PRAG 2018a (cf. preliminary summary in SEG 59.1100 and the lengthy new summary in SEG 68.727; *ed. pr.* SCIBONA 2009); PRESTIANNI GIALLOMBARDO 2018a. Note also further observations on the institutions in CAPPELLETTI 2020a.

inscription and on several brick stamps, formed of a large *pi* surmounted by a small *omicron* and enclosing an *alpha*, should be resolved as $\pi\acute{o}(\lambda\iota\varsigma) \text{ } \Lambda(\lambda\alpha\iota\sigma\acute{\iota}\nu\omega\nu)$ and not as $\text{ } \Lambda\pi\acute{o}(\lambda\lambda\omega\nu\omicron\varsigma)$.⁴² Prestianni Giallombardo also republishes the associated and rediscovered fragmentary stone inscription set up by the same *koinon*.⁴³

Despite the spectacular nature of the Nemenios bronzes, the most significant gain for Halaesan epigraphy in this period must be the publication by Emiliano Arena of a series of seven new fragments from the site, in a fundamental study which puts our understanding of the long-lost cadastral inscription on a completely new footing.⁴⁴ In order to enable a complete reassessment, Arena republishes in detail both the second lost fragment of the cadastral inscription published by Di Giovanni in 1885 and another fragmentary text found in 1958 and published by Calderone.⁴⁵ The first two of the new fragments published by Arena are convincingly argued to be parts of the lost cadastral text, of which we now therefore have four fragments (that from the antiquarian tradition, that published in 1885, and Arena's nos. 1 and 2).⁴⁶ One very significant gain is that we now have surviving physical evidence of the original form of the cadastral inscription, which together with the antiquarian record enables the conclusion that the inscription originally consisted of at least two stelae, possibly inserted into a structure rather than free-standing, since no surviving piece has a worked and finished reverse. Almost certainly these were located in a monumental context physically distinct from the agora and somewhat to the south, in the vicinity of the later mediaeval church of S. Maria dei Palazzi. The specific choice of stone employed, similar to that of the 1958 fragment and that of Arena's fragment no.4 (below), marks a specific choice for such public epigraphy, a fine (but relatively soft) limestone from some 60km eastward along the Sicilian coast in the vicinity of Tindari, distinct from the coarser local stone used for the majority of the Hellenistic honorifics at the site.⁴⁷ Close analysis by Arena of both the 1958 fragment (Arena's no.3) and his own fourth fragment enables the convincing reconstruction of a substantial monumental public dossier. The 1958 fragment is persuasively demonstrated to be not, as argued for example by Calderone and Manganaro, a part of the terms and process for leasing of the land, the *synthekai*, but instead to describe a process for the assessing of claims of ownership in the context of the determination of the allotment of land, probably by the state – a process which is assumed to precede the final description of the land allotment as it is presented in the four fragments of the main *tabulae*. Arena's new fragment no.4 is then demonstrated to be the first Sicilian example of *misthosis* (compare the Tavole di Eraclea), a contract for the leasing by the city of the plots described in the *tabulae* fragments to lessees, whether individual citizens or groups of citizens.⁴⁸ Given that the *tabulae* themselves already contain various prescriptions for leasing within them (specific restrictions relating to individual plots of land, as well as prescriptions as to which citizen groups were able to lease some of the plots of land), this new contract document is suggested to be the record of an actual contract for a specific act of leasing at a particular moment in time to specified

⁴² PRESTIANNI GIALLOMBARDO 2018b (although arguments about the dates of the various texts concerned are far from definitive, since none of these texts can be tightly or securely dated relative to one another).

⁴³ IG XIV.354 (ISic001176 = PRAG, TIGANO 2017, no. 3); PRESTIANNI GIALLOMBARDO 2017 (the relevance first noted by SCIBONA 2009, 108).

⁴⁴ ARENA 2020a (see now ARENA 2023 for a convenient summary). The original principal fragment of the cadastral inscription is IG XIV.352 (ISic001174 fr.A).

⁴⁵ DI GIOVANNI 1885, now ARENA 2020a, 89 (ISic001174 fr.B); CALDERONE 1961, now ARENA 2020a, no.3 (ISic003651).

⁴⁶ ARENA 2020a, no.1 (ISic001174 fr.C); ARENA 2020a, no.2 (ISic001174 fr.D); cf. ARENA 2018a.

⁴⁷ ARENA 2020a, 5 note 1.

⁴⁸ ARENA 2020a, no.4 (ISic004407; also ARENA 2020b).

individuals. The final four fragments presented by Arena (his nos. 5-8) are too small to allow for comparable analysis and integration, although it is highly likely that no. 6 is part of an honorific decree.⁴⁹ In sum, the epigraphic evidence from Halaesa is now clearly amongst the most important from Hellenistic Sicily, the cadastral dossier matched for importance only by the financial inscriptions from Tauromenium or the Entella tablets, and the civic corpus as a whole by that of Segesta.

Besides the corpora for Segesta and Halaesa, the city that has produced the most new, and most original material in this period is undoubtedly ancient Messina. Given the city's location on the Straits, this should not perhaps surprise, but it is only through the recent work of the Soprintendenza in the areas of the city's ancient necropoleis in particular, that this has become more visible. A series of five Greek funerary inscriptions from the Roman imperial period, published by Giuseppina Zavettieri, enrich the corpus and shift the balance of surviving funerary material from Messina slightly further in favour of the use of Greek.⁵⁰ However, perhaps the most remarkable text from Messina is the verse dedication to Orion as protector of the city, from the first or second century CE.⁵¹ The text was unfortunately found in secondary deposition, but with its Homeric echoes provides an important example of the use of literary Greek in the Imperial period, in a votive and at least semi-public context - quite apart from its contribution to the mythical imaginary of the Straits.⁵² However, in addition to the new material from the Imperial period, we now have several important texts bridging the gap between the Oscan inscriptions of the third century BCE and the imperial necropoleis. In collaboration with the Soprintendenza, Emiliano Arena has published two cinerary vases recording women with Oscan names written in Greek: the first, from the third century BCE, incised, records one *Novia Oppia*; the second, painted, probably of the second century BCE, one *Pakua Pontia*.⁵³ The latter text preserves the Oscan style of nomenclature (praenomen and gentilicium), but transformed with Greek genitive endings and age at death in the distinctively Sicilian ascending numerals (on numerals see further below). In addition to these, Arena has also published another Hellenistic funerary inscription, which offers a striking example of a painted funerary aedicola, more familiar from mainland Greece, originally from atop an *epitymbion* monument.⁵⁴ The onomastics of the deceased, Basiliskos son of Boudelos, are themselves of considerable interest, well elucidated by Arena: Basiliskos is rare, but one Gnaeus Pompeius Basiliscus is recorded by Cicero at Messina (Cic. *Verr.* 4.25), likely a relative; the unparalleled name Boudelos might be an unusual Greek form (a diminutive from *bous*), a Sikel name, or even of Oscan derivation.

The last site which deserves to be singled out is Himera. Work continues on elucidating the important but challenging late Archaic law on lead published in 1997: in separate studies Antonietta Brugnone and Olga Tribulato draw attention to the interest of the presence of *phratryai* and *phylai* in the text.⁵⁵ Tribulato presents a very thorough re-examination of the text and the language of the inscription (noting that the *lamina* is essentially intact on all sides, implying potentially further

⁴⁹ ARENA 2020a, no.5 (ISic001694); no. 6 (ISic001695); no. 7 (ISic001696); no. 8 (ISic001698).

⁵⁰ ZAVETTIERI 2017 (ISic004377, ISic004378, ISic004380, ISic004381, ISic004382); cf. KORHONEN 2011, 13-14 for the last attempted assessment, noting an equal balance of Greek and Latin.

⁵¹ OLLÀ 2017 (ISic004383); further discussion in CASTRIZIO, MELIADÒ 2020 and ARENA 2020c.

⁵² For this topic, note the re-study by CARUSO 2017 of the Hellenistic sanctuary in the catacomb of S.Lucia, Siracusa, which includes a named depiction of Zeus Peloros and Porthmos (ISic001867), the personification of the Straits.

⁵³ ARENA 2021a (ISic020917, *Novia Oppia*; and ISic020918, *Pakua Pontia*).

⁵⁴ ARENA 2021b (ISic004384); preliminary notice in BURGIO 2017, 86 fig. 4 and 103 note 10.

⁵⁵ BRUGNONE 2018a and TRIBULATO 2019 (*SEG* 47.1431 = ISic030326).

plaques if the original text was longer), and argues that the law is not one for the redistribution of land allotments but rather a measure intended to prevent reassignment of existing allotments. In a parallel study, building in part on the detailed analysis of the land law Tribulato has also reconsidered the traditionally thorny question of the nature of the Greek used at Himera.⁵⁶ The Himeran corpus is notoriously small, making such analysis challenging. In a typically understated paper, Antonietta Brugnone recapitulates the entire Himeran corpus with a focus on alphabetical forms, before presenting in an appendix some 28 previously unpublished epigraphic fragments from past excavations in the 'area sacra' of the Piano di Imera:⁵⁷ nos. 1-4 are fragments of bronze *laminæ* (the longest has 3-4 letters from each of 4 lines); nos. 5-24 are ceramic fragments with graffitied texts, sometimes only a single letter or symbol; no. 25 is a fragment of a marble *louterion*, apparently bearing an omega, although frustratingly no image or drawing is provided to indicate the context of the letter or elucidate its form; nos. 26-28 are amphora fragments bearing marks. However, most of this pales into insignificance alongside the spectacular finds emerging from the recent excavation (2008-2011, 2018) of c.10,000 tombs (late 7th to late 5th century BCE) in the western necropolis area of Buonfornello (in conjunction with the redevelopment of the Palermo-Messina railway). Antonietta Brugnone, Alba Maria Gabriella Calascibetta and Stefano Vassallo present a preliminary overview of the 54 lead *defixiones* recovered from these excavations, alongside the first publication in detail of two of these.⁵⁸ All belong to the period of the fifth century BCE and not only greatly increase the already substantial corpus of early Sicilian *defixiones* (principally from Selinunte) but offer an unparalleled body of material with a fully documented archaeological context. The excavators cannot identify any obvious pattern in the burials associated with these *defixiones* (although there is a prevalence of inhumation burials). All are on lead, most are quadrangular in form, almost all are folded or rolled and many are pierced by a nail, which is preserved in some cases. Several were found within a burial, others in immediate association. The most striking instance, however, is the association of a group of 45 *defixiones* with a single burial (otherwise unremarkable, and itself containing two *defixiones* belonging to the moment of burial), all found in and around the pile of stones marking the burial – and also in association with fragments of bronze graters. The authors publish two of the *defixiones* in full, the first a *lamina* in a rare quarter-circle shape, bearing on one side an incised drawing of a male figure accompanying a male name, and on the other a female figure and a female name – a feature without parallel; the second, rather more typically, bears a list of names in column format on each side.⁵⁹

Although much the most spectacular discovery, the Himera *defixiones* are not the only additions to the ever-growing Sicilian curse corpus.⁶⁰ Megara Hyblaea and Solunto can now be added to the locations providing Hellenistic *defixiones*, increasing the number of post-Classical *defixiones* to c.17: that from Megara Hyblaea, from the vicinity of House XV.B, is a judicial *defixio* with several Greek names, dated on palaeographic grounds (elements including rhomboid omicron and theta and closed omega) by Federica Cordano to the late third or second century BCE; that from Solunto, bearing just a pair of Greek names, one male and one female, is also dated by Laura di Leonardo on palaeographic grounds (e.g. lunate epsilon and sigma, small omicron) between the later third and first centuries BCE.⁶¹ A third Greek *defixio* from the early imperial period has been published by

⁵⁶ TRIBULATO 2018a.

⁵⁷ BRUGNONE 2017a.

⁵⁸ BRUGNONE, CALASCIBETTA, VASSALLO 2020.

⁵⁹ BRUGNONE, CALASCIBETTA, VASSALLO 2020, 71-85 Laminetta HA26825 (ISic030323); 85-91 Laminetta HA19390 (ISic030324).

⁶⁰ Note also the minor re-reading of IGDS 134B = SEG 57.905B (ISic030019) by WILSON, FAVI 2017.

⁶¹ CORDANO, ROCCA 2018 (ISic030322); DI LEONARDO 2020 (ISic030321).

Bevilacqua, Bettarini and Rocca: the text is said to be from Selinunte, which would be unusual for the date⁶² – but as one of 15 tablets in private hands some of which remain unpublished, it seems necessary to raise concerns regarding the ethics of the continued practice of publication of unprovenanced materials in private hands.⁶³ These additions to the corpus can now be considered against the overview provided by Thea Sommerschild, whose compilation of the material in a database (*ISicDef*) is in turn providing the basis for the steady incorporation of the material into *I.Sicily*.⁶⁴ Several *defixiones* have also been the subject of further study.⁶⁵

Beyond the specific corpus of lead *defixiones* the epigraphy on metal of the island also continues to attract attention, with a mixture of new material and revisions. Among the early material on lead, there is now a detailed collection of studies on the fragmentary verse text donated to the Getty and thought to be from Selinunte;⁶⁶ study of the *lex sacra* from Selinunte also continues.⁶⁷ Paolo Mazzei rediscusses and contextualises against the larger corpus of such texts the gold ‘orphyic’ lamina from the site of Entella.⁶⁸ Pier Giovanni Guzzo has argued that the fragments of a sixth-century BCE Chalcidic Greek legal text preserved on bronze at the site of Monte San Mauro should be assumed to come from a secondary context of bronze hoarding in the earlier fifth century BCE, and that Orsi’s archaeological reports demonstrate the lack of any connection with the buildings in the vicinity of which they were recovered.⁶⁹ The original events are ultimately unrecoverable, but he notes that the text most likely comes from Leontini or its *apoikia* at Eubea. Valentina Mignosa offers a new edition of the fragmentary decree from the area of Palazzolo Acreide which mentions the Syracusan *gamoroi*, arguing for a slightly earlier date than is normally assumed (late 6th cent. BCE), and so breaking the direct link with the Herodotean report of the exile of the *gamoroi* to Kasmenai.⁷⁰ Lastly, among the earlier material, Federica Cordano and Giovanni di Stefano publish a further fourteen *tesserae* from the sanctuary of Athena at Camarina, while Cordano also revisits the text of *tessera* no.6, highlighting that it is not in fact a *tessera*, but a lead *lamina* recording a dedication at the sanctuary.⁷¹

Moving to the Hellenistic period, and complementing the detailed study of the two Halaesa tablets on bronze noted above (in which Prag provides an assessment of the use of bronze and of honorific decrees from the island), Anthony Bonanno has undertaken a long overdue re-edition of the stylistically similar Maltese proxeny decree for Demetrios son of Diodotos of Syracuse (the same man is honoured in a comparable Agrigentine decree).⁷² Among such public decrees on bronze, the

⁶² ROCCA 2020 (edition), BEVILACQUA 2020 (study), BETTARINI 2020 (linguistics) (ISic030328).

⁶³ Readers might consider the policy of the Archaeological Institute of America, as adopted by the AJA (<https://www.ajaonline.org/submissions/antiquities-policy>, accessed 02.02.2024).

⁶⁴ SOMMERSCHILD 2019, including distribution maps for different chronological periods and a concordance; note too the recent discussion of Sicilian cursing in LAMONT 2022. The recent *sylloge of defixiones* in the Roman West (post-400 BCE) by SÁNCHEZ NATALÍAS 2022, because of its decision to omit texts in Greek, references only a single Sicilian text for the post-classical period (ISic030109) and therefore presents a singularly misleading picture for the island.

⁶⁵ BERNABÉ, MARTÍN HERNÁNDEZ 2020 on SEG 49.1301 (ISic030109) from Marsala, and RIVOLI 2021 on SEG 29.930 (ISic030079) from Morgantina.

⁶⁶ ANTONETTI 2018 on SEG 66.1067 (ISic030316); see also LUCARINI 2018.

⁶⁷ GIANGIULIO 2021 on SEG 43.630 = CGRN 13 (ISic030112) (and see ANTONETTI in the previous note).

⁶⁸ MAZZEI 2018 on SEG 52.906 (ISic030318).

⁶⁹ GUZZO 2019 on SEG 4.64 (ISic030042).

⁷⁰ MIGNOSA 2021 on SEG 4.27 (ISic030002).

⁷¹ CORDANO, DI STEFANO 2017; CORDANO 2020 on SEG 42.846 (ISic030142).

⁷² BONANNO 2017 on IG XIV.953 (ISic030280); the Agrigento text is IG XIV.952 (ISic030279). Readers might wish to note the fragment of a bronze text from Monte Iato, now available at ISic030048.

Entella tablets retain their fascination. Carmine Ampolo has now provided a detailed account of the tortuous history of their emergence into the public domain following the original clandestine discovery on the slopes above the public area of the site of Entella, which almost certainly occurred in the first half of 1977.⁷³ Meantime, Mario Lombardo has offered perhaps the most convincing reconstruction of the likely historical context for the tablets. Subverting the widespread assumption of modern scholars that the Entellans were driven out by the Carthaginians he offers strong arguments in favour of the main precursor to the decrees being an attack on the city by the Romans in the early phases of the First Punic War, whence the deliberate posturing of the renewal of treaties pertaining to an earlier conflict against the Carthaginians, the (necessary) support of Rome's allies the Segestans, and the need to honour a Roman *praefectus*, all in the context of subsequent resettlement under Roman hegemony.⁷⁴

Unsurprisingly, the largest number of new inscriptions is in the domain of funerary epigraphy, which generally predominates in the epigraphic record. Several examples have already been noted above, both the archaic funerary inscription from Ragusa Ibla and the series of Hellenistic and Roman texts from Messana. Even if epigraphic finds are always somewhat random, the distributions and concentrations of funerary epigraphy on the island are extremely uneven and it remains far from clear to what extent local or regional habits of funerary culture affect the survival to a greater or lesser degree than the accidents of later occupation, rebuilding and archaeological excavation. Emblematic is the rich Hellenistic necropolis of remote Abakainon (Tripi) in the north-east of the island (to be contrasted with the almost complete absence, for example, of funerary inscriptions in the Segestan corpus).⁷⁵ A series of studies by Girolamo Sofia have increased the accessibility of this particular set of material: alongside several studies of the typology of the *epitymbion* monuments of the necropolis, Sofia also publishes seven previously unpublished epitaphs, bringing the total number, by my count, to 18, alongside two further fragmentary texts.⁷⁶ One of the notable features in this necropolis is the very uneven presence of inscriptions; doubtless some texts were painted, but it is also a timely reminder that not every funerary monument necessarily bore a text, and more work is needed to explore the relationship of inscribed and unscribed monuments.

Two further archaic epitaphs are now known also from Selinunte, one published by Antonietta Brugnone, repeating the familiar *oimoi* formula; the second, recording the name Selinis, reported by Rosella Giglio, will be published shortly.⁷⁷ An epitaph from Hellenistic Syracuse, identified in the Museo Archeologico Regionale "Paolo Orsi" as part of the *I.Sicily* work to complete the cataloguing of the museum's epigraphic collection, presents a remarkable and near unique painted relief inscription, recording one Nikasis, son of Aristokrates.⁷⁸ It deserves emphasising that, as so often, what Sicily perhaps lacks in purely quantitative terms, epigraphically, is made up for by the variety and originality of the material. The existing corpus of funerary material has also been the focus of ongoing research. Olga Tribulato offers a detailed reconsideration of the small corpus of 8 inscribed Greek epigrams from the island (four dedicatory, four funerary), while Antonietta Brugnone

⁷³ AMPOLO 2021b (for the texts, see now ISic030294-ISic030301).

⁷⁴ LOMBARDO 2018.

⁷⁵ *I.Segesta* G26 (ISic002942) is the only possible Greek example, and the editors rightly note that it seems more likely to be an honorific base than a funerary inscription as Nenci originally proposed.

⁷⁶ For the inscriptions, see SOFIA 2018 (ISic004411-004422, of which 4415-4421 are *inedita*); cf. SOFIA 2019a and SOFIA 2019b on the site and the monuments.

⁷⁷ BRUGNONE 2018b (ISic004379); preliminary notice in GIGLIO CERNIGLIA 2019, 211, full edition forthcoming in the journal *Elymos*, vol. 2 (ISic004436).

⁷⁸ PRAG 2017 (ISic003387).

republishes the Greek funerary texts from Mozia and elucidates features of several funerary inscriptions from Messana, Lilybaeum (Marsala) and Licodia Eubea.⁷⁹ The later Christian funerary epigraphy has also seen various studies with reference both to the catacombs and to rupestral contexts in the south-east of the island.⁸⁰

To complete the survey of new inscriptions, note firstly a pair of mosaic texts, both examples of the well attested $\chi\alpha\tilde{\iota}\rho\epsilon$ type – one from Solunto, of the first century BCE, black letters on a white mosaic background; and the other from Centuripe, of the Republican period, black letters framed by a white rounded tabula ansata, on a red cocciopesto floor.⁸¹ Secondly, Antonietta Brugnone publishes a ceramic incense burner recovered from the Selinunte museum stores (from the necropolis in Manicalunga), bearing a dedication to Athena, probably of the fourth/third century BCE.⁸² Lastly, and in tribute to the late Henri Tréziny, two recent acquisitions from Megara Hyblaea: a small Hellenistic altar dedicated to Aphrodite published in the magisterial *Megara Hyblaea* VII volume edited by Tréziny,⁸³ and what appears to be a boundary marker, of probably late Roman date, albeit in Greek, and which is a second example of an already attested *terminus* from the site found in the 1960s.⁸⁴

This last text was in fact already documented in the *Taccuini* of Paolo Orsi, having entered the Siracusa museum by 1890, and readers' attention is drawn to the monumental publication of the first four of Orsi's *taccuini* in 2018 by Gioconda Lamagna and Giuseppina Monterosso – itself the first in a planned series, of which the second volume is now also published.⁸⁵ The first volume in particular is an epigraphic goldmine, containing Orsi's transcriptions of the several hundred texts present in the archaeological museum of Siracusa upon his arrival in 1888 – and in many cases these are superior to subsequent published editions.⁸⁶ The two volumes published to date cover a mere 16 of the 150 notebooks that survive and there is a wealth of material still to come. The point to emphasise here is the need for increased attention to the antiquarian and archival record not least for its contribution to the island's epigraphy. Among many under-used resources, one might note Julius Schubring's autopsy notes from the 1860s, now in the *CIL* archives at Berlin. Leading exponents of this work in recent years have included Francesco Muscolino, with particular reference to the Tauromenium corpus (most recently re-editing a lost pavement inscription from the antiquarian record);⁸⁷ and Kalle Korhonen, who has made similarly careful use of the antiquarian

⁷⁹ TRIBULATO 2018b; BRUGNONE 2017b (ISic001546, 003107, 003108); BRUGNONE 2020 (*IG* XIV.254 = ISic001074); BRUGNONE 2021a (*SEG* 34.955 = ISic003070; ISic004380).

⁸⁰ RIZZONE 2017 (on the territory of Santa Croce Camerina); RIZZONE, SAMMITO 2021 (on prestige burials in catacomb contexts); BEVILACQUA 2021 restudying ORSI, *NSA* 1895, no.225 (ISic001868), and CARRA BONACASA 2021 (on the Villagrazia di Carini catacomb, inscriptions previously studied by FALZONE 2014).

⁸¹ Solunto: PORTALE, MILAZZO, MONTALI 2020, 166 and fig. 12.c (ISic001672); Centuripe: BIONDI, RIZZA 2017, 21 with fig.11 and BIONDI 2020, 305 with fig. 35 (ISic004515).

⁸² BRUGNONE 2018c (ISic020942); the paper concludes with observations on *IG* XIV.217 (ISic001038) from Akrai.

⁸³ TRÉZINY 2018, 206 (ISic004405) (note the late fourth-century BCE *skyphos* with a graffito dedication to Aphrodite on the same page, not in *SEG*, now ISic020943).

⁸⁴ Referenced in TRÉZINY 2018, 275 note 11 (for 'J.Craig', read 'J.Prag'). Tréziny generously helped to clarify the relationship between the texts; the second text is now published as ISic004389, not in *SEG*; the first is *SEG* 26.1096 (ISic003698).

⁸⁵ ORSI 2018 (edited by Gioconda LAMAGNA and Giuseppina MONTEROSSO); and ORSI 2022 (Giuseppina MONTEROSSO); the project has long been championed by the indefatigable Paola Pelagatti.

⁸⁶ PRAG 2021b offers a detailed discussion with examples.

⁸⁷ MUSCOLINO 2017 on *IG* XIV.446 (ISic001271).

evidence to clarify the status of texts from Trapani, Messina and Catania.⁸⁸ In similar vein, as part of the *I. Sicily* work, it has recently been possible through a more attentive study of the earlier publication record, to reattribute one of the few Hellenistic Greek funerary inscriptions from Catania to the site of Enna.⁸⁹

Beyond such research in the archival and antiquarian records, work continues on previously published texts. Notwithstanding its place at the head of the *IG* volume, the inscription from the steps of the Apollonion in Syracusae continues to attract attempts to resolve its various *crucis*, with Philip Sapistein bringing sophisticated imaging techniques to the problem, while Riccardo di Cesare has undertaken a comprehensive re-evaluation of previous editions.⁹⁰ Federica Cordano has re-examined the unusual Archaic marble dedication to Enyo from Naxos.⁹¹ The rich material from Tauromenium continues to provide a focus for attention: on the one hand, Lorenzo Campagna has now provided the first serious material evaluation of the surviving blocks of the account inscriptions and their likely physical context;⁹² and on the other, Filippo Battistoni, building on extensive autopsy work with the end goal of a new edition, has made further progress on the relative and absolute chronology of the *stratagoi* list, while also re-examining the evidence for civic *sigla* (see below).⁹³ Alessia Dimartino has also provided a thorough republication of the various monumental seat inscriptions to be found in the immediate vicinity of the theatre, as part of a broader series of republications of theatre texts from Syracusae and Morgantina also.⁹⁴

Moving outwards to more thematic considerations, several particular topics that depend upon epigraphic evidence remain of perennial interest, notably *sigla* and onomastics, institutions, and numerals. In addition to the discussion of the case of Tauromenium by Battistoni just noted, the decree for Nemenios at Halaesa and the fragmentary decree from Kale Akte (Caronia) have provided the basis for further discussion of the so-called ‘demotic’ abbreviations that seem to be widespread across eastern Sicily in particular.⁹⁵ Emiliano Arena has provided a comprehensive overview of the Hellenistic evidence for such abbreviated ‘third name’ elements in Sicily (commonly three-letter abbreviations), leaving open the question of whether they should truly be considered demotics with, e.g., a topographical association; and drawing the not unreasonable (or new) conclusion that these imply considerable institutional commonality across the region after Timoleon. Federica Cordano offers a more summary overview, which however ranges back to the earlier evidence from Camarina and Naxos that ties in to tribal and phratry divisions.⁹⁶ Alex Walthall and Randall Souza have now moved this discussion into a different area, with the publication of two terracotta spheres bearing

⁸⁸ KORHONEN 2017a, demonstrating that a number of inscriptions attributed to ancient Drepanon (Trapani, *SEG* 52.892-905) are antiquarian inventions; and KORHONEN 2018 arguing that a series of connected texts from Messina, *IG* XIV.402 (ISic001227 and ISic001228), *SEG* 42.870 (ISic001230), and *IG* XIV.412 (ISic001239) are all almost certainly from Cilicia originally; and that *IG* XIV.349bis (ISic003352) from Catania is an antiquarian invention.

⁸⁹ *SEG* 54.899 (ISic003110). Note also the recent rediscussion by FUDULI 2017 of the temple / context to which *IG* XIV.369 (ISic001192) is attributed.

⁹⁰ *IG* XIV.1 (ISic000822): SAPISTEIN 2019, 2021; DI CESARE 2020.

⁹¹ CORDANO 2018a on *SEG* 35.1014 (ISic001425).

⁹² CAMPAGNA 2018.

⁹³ BATTISTONI 2018, 2020.

⁹⁴ DIMARTINO 2017a, 2017b, 2017c.

⁹⁵ PRAG 2018a, 115-118 on the Halaesa text; ARENA 2017 and 2019 (essentially the same paper) with primary reference to *SEG* 59.1102 (ISic003628) from Kale Akte.

⁹⁶ CORDANO 2018b.

names engraved after firing, from Hellenistic Morgantina.⁹⁷ Although these examples do not include such ‘demotic’ abbreviations, Walthall and Souza assemble the relevant Sicilian evidence in considerable detail in order to make a convincing case that these objects (for which parallels of varying types can be found across the island) are lots for the purposes of sortition (as described, e.g., in the Nakone tablet from Entella). More specific discussion of individual institutions has been provided both by Emiliano Arena, revisiting the nature of the *synkletos* at Kale Akte and the evidence for tricameral organisation in Sicily and by Loredana Cappelletti’s examination of the office of *amphipolos* at Syracusae and Centuripae (the latter with reference specifically to *IG XIV.574* (ISic001393), speculating that the office might also have been eponymous).⁹⁸

However, all of this rather pales besides the quite remarkable study by Paul Iversen of the evidence of the ‘Antikythera Mechanism’ for the ‘Corinthian family of calendars’, of which the Sicilian calendars (as attested at Akrai, Tauromenium and Syracusae) are an important sub-group.⁹⁹ Earlier studies of the mechanism speculated that it might pertain to the Syracusan calendar (which of course allowed for the seductive link to Archimedes, picked up in turn by Hollywood’s *Indiana Jones and the Dial of Destiny* (2023)). This leads Iversen to devote a substantial preliminary discussion to the calendars of Tauromenium, Syracusae and Akrai, with the primary purpose of showing that the Syracusan calendar is not that of the mechanism, but with the secondary result of clarifying the complete calendar of Tauromenium, and convincingly arguing that it is the same as that of Syracusae (and probably Akrai), although the latter two calendars are incompletely attested.¹⁰⁰ The detailed discussion includes the persuasive reading of the month Ἐλώρειος in *IG XIV.426*, col. 2, line 5 (ISic001251, Tauromenium), and comprehensive discussion of the significance of that name (linked undoubtedly to Heloros and an associated festival); but also includes an extremely balanced review of the associated evidence of the three-letter abbreviations in a variety of texts of uncertain provenance (and, like Prag and Arena, rejecting the idea that overlap in the use of these abbreviations can be used to argue for provenance).¹⁰¹ Beyond the Sicilian specifics, however, in the full elucidation of the Corinthian calendar Iversen succeeds in anchoring the months to the seasons, and as part of his extensive use of the Magnesia-on-the-Maeander *asylia* decrees can even offer the conclusion that the Magnesian envoys were in Syracusae between 27 October and 4 November 208 BCE.¹⁰²

The use of numerals in Sicilian Greek epigraphy remains a complicated and fascinating subject, which overlaps with the discussions noted in the preceding paragraphs. The extensive use of so-called ‘pseudo-ascending’ numerals in Sicily prior to the Augustan age is part of a review of the use of numerals more general in eastern Sicily by Federica Cordano, and she offers the hypothesis that

⁹⁷ WALTHALL, SOUZA 2021.

⁹⁸ ARENA 2019; CAPPELLETTI 2020b and 2020c; note more generally the resources gathered under Cappelletti’s direction at <https://www.arcait.it/en/> (accessed 04.02.2024).

⁹⁹ IVERSEN 2017; whether due to the date of publication, or a failure to recognise its relevance, it is unfortunate that Iversen’s work has seemingly not yet impacted upon Sicilian studies.

¹⁰⁰ IVERSEN 2017, 130-141 and esp. 132 table 1 for the Tauromenium calendar.

¹⁰¹ IVERSEN 2017, 131-133 with figs. 2-4 and 139-140 for the re-reading, facilitated by the ongoing study of the Tauromenium accounts by Filippo Battistoni; the same month name is, as IVERSEN notes (see 140 note 45), also attested now at Halaesa in the Nemenios bronze (ISic030277). On the abbreviations, see IVERSEN 2017, 137-139.

¹⁰² For the Magnesian envoys, IVERSEN 2017, 188-191; more generally on the alignment of months and seasons, pp. 164-185 (note, e.g., Syracusan *Karneios* in the early Autumn, and specifically 13 September to 11 October in 413 BCE, at p.166). Note additionally his detailed reconsideration of the pre-ambles of the Syracusan decree at Magnesia (*I. Magnesia* 72, lines 1-6), pp. 134-136.

this is perhaps linked closely to the Sicilian weight system (specifically the Sicilian *litra*). The discussion of the phenomenon as it occurs on precious metal objects in Hellenistic Sicily, by Pier Giovanni Guzzo might well be thought to add weight to this suggestion.¹⁰³ Cordano's review includes some examination of the variation between ordinals written in full and with symbols (acrophonic or alphabetic), and fresh material for the discussion is now provided by the new inscriptions from Halaesa presented by Emiliano Arena (see above). The latter appear to include both acrophonic and alphabetic numbers within the same (cadastral) text, as well as possibly local variants of acrophonic numerals.¹⁰⁴ As a minor outcome of the *I.Sicily* project, it might be added that an instance of what seem to be acrophonic numerals in a lost inscription from Mineo, reported originally by Corrado Tamburino Merlini and noted by Orsi in 1900, and in turn offering a parallel for the problematic numerals in the galleries of the Castello Eurialo, do not so far seem to have been integrated into the discussion, precisely because of their obscurity.¹⁰⁵ Discussion of numerals overlaps necessarily with other *sigla* and abbreviations, and Arena presents and discusses a revised reading of what appears to be an abbreviation for the land unit, *moros*, in the Di Giovanni Halaesa fragment.¹⁰⁶

Perhaps the single greatest growth area in the study of Sicilian epigraphy in recent years is the increasing focus on the socio-linguistic study of the epigraphic material, although such work has been on the rise for almost twenty years.¹⁰⁷ Sicilian Greek, and the persistence of its distinctive form of Doric has long been studied. Olga Tribulato offers a methodologically rich close reading of the small corpus of Sicilian Archaic and Classical epigrams, while Livia Tagliapietra has recently reassessed the potential saliency of the choice of Doric forms in their continued use down to at least the Augustan period.¹⁰⁸ However, a greater degree of attention is now being focused upon the interaction (or interference) between Greek and Latin on the island in the Roman period: while the overlap between the two languages in the Roman period has of course long been recognised, the increasing sophistication of bilingualism studies, and the recognition that Sicily in the Roman imperial period is an area where texts are likely to reflect a bilingual situation and so display features that reveal that situation, is generating increasingly rich levels of analysis.¹⁰⁹ Mario Mazza surveys the situation for later Roman Sicily but, in a paper which reviews the classical studies of Manganaro in particular, effectively stops with the rise of modern bilingualism studies and the work of Jim Adams and others, c.2003.¹¹⁰ In fact, that date marks the moment from which Kalle Korhonen above

¹⁰³ CORDANO 2017 and GUZZO 2017, both part of a volume dedicated to the use of numerals in Greek epigraphy.

¹⁰⁴ See ARENA 2018b on the numerals specifically, but also ARENA 2020a, esp. 91-94.

¹⁰⁵ ISic003438 (ORSI, *RSA* 5, 1900, 57 no.35).

¹⁰⁶ ARENA 2020a, 89-94 on ISic001174 frag.b (note that ARENA's suggestion that there are also two different acrophonic forms of the numeral ten might perhaps be resolved by reading the new form (*delta + omicron*) attested in ARENA's no. 4 (ISic004407) as another abbreviation of similar form to the one discussed here). A review of the monograms and ligatured letters found in the Halaesa texts prior to the publication of these new fragments is provided by PRESTIANNI GIALLOMBARDO 2018b.

¹⁰⁷ See especially the papers in TRIBULATO 2012.

¹⁰⁸ TRIBULATO 2018b; TAGLIAPIETRA 2018; on Sicilian Doric more generally, WILLI 2008 and MIMBRERA Olarte 2012.

¹⁰⁹ See ADAMS 2003, 7-8 and 30 for the gradation from biversion bilinguals to texts 'implicitly reflecting bilingual situations', and the revised typology and discussion in MULLEN 2013, 74-94. ESTARÁN TOLOSA 2016, a monumental catalogue of bilingual epigraphy in the Roman West, focuses on bi-version texts, but specifically those where Latin is in contact with a 'vernacular' language (a category chosen to exclude Greek when discussing the Roman West), with the misleading result that there appears to be no bilingual material in Sicily (where Greek was, however, the 'vernacular' language by the Roman period).

¹¹⁰ MAZZA 2018. The 'classic' paper of MANGANARO 1993 which Mazza cites as fundamental ('Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.') is in fact so selective in its choice of material as to be fundamentally misleading (citing 60 texts, of which perhaps 4 are pre-300 CE, 45 are Latin, and all come from

all has pioneered this work in Sicilian studies; Korhonen summarises some of his findings, emphasising this bilingual situation, in a recent paper on the Augustan colonies.¹¹¹ In collaboration with Cristina Soraci he has also briefly turned this particular lense on some of the striking examples of Greek in public epigraphy of the Augustan period, helping to move away from an overly schematic use of such material for narrowly political or institutional history.¹¹² The most famous ‘true’ bilingual from Sicily, the stone-cutter’s shop-sign from Palermo continues to attract intense debate, with no fewer than four new discussions:¹¹³ Rossana De Simone explores further Olga Tribulato’s suggestion (after Kaibel) that the text’s apparent oddities in both Greek and Latin might reflect a Punic speaker’s authorship; Emmanuele Castelli takes a different approach, revisiting the significance of the vocabulary for the stone-cutter’s work in the initial lines and, in what seems like a rather forced argument, suggesting that they describe not simply the preparation of inscriptions but the carving of the stelai or columns themselves; perhaps most convincingly, Patrick James and Moreed Arbabzadah summarise the linguistic peculiarities of the text and reprise a passing suggestion of Peter Kruschwitz, that the problematic *cum operum publicorum* of the Latin text conceals an ellipse, and that if one reads *cum (titulis) operum publicorum* all the difficulties dissolve and the Greek text can be shown to be a verbatim translation of a native Latin speaker’s original. Most recently, Carlo Consani confirms this interpretation while offering a sharp methodological critique of previous discussions. Even if this might finally put the debate to bed, the stone continues to serve as a constant reminder of Sicily’s rich multilingualism in this period. Equally emblematic is the ancient city of Lilybaeum: the rich additions to the Lilybaeum corpus in the years immediately preceding this survey’s focus have been conveniently summarised by Rosella Giglio and Rossana De Simone, while Antonietta Brugnone and Paolo Poccetti provide detailed studies of some of the most remarkable texts from this city in order to highlight the ways in which they reflect its position at a true linguistic crossroads of the Mediterranean.¹¹⁴

Lastly, mention must be made of Rebecca Henzel’s study of honorific statues for Sicily, covering the period from the 3rd century BCE to the 5th century CE - while not narrowly epigraphic, it is of importance to any epigraphic study, as well as to any study of civic life and institutions of Greek and Roman Sicily. The heart of the work is a comprehensive catalogue of well over 400 attested honorific statues (based upon archaeological, epigraphic, and literary evidence), in which the author identifies a number of apparently idiosyncratic trends: Hellenistic honorific statue culture comes relatively late to Sicily, weakly attested before the second century;¹¹⁵ moreover, statue bases remain surprisingly low in height throughout this period (a typical upper limit of c.60cm), understood to imply a lower level of competition for prominence than is to be seen in the Hellenistic east; locations for such statues are similarly limited, concentrating upon the agora and the urban core. The principal increase in activity would seem to post-date the fall of Carthage, and the accompanying shift in the place of Sicily in the central Mediterranean (which is in line with the contemporary rise in urban

the south-east of the island – when most texts of this date on the island are Greek). Cf. MOLÈ VENTURA 2018 for a study focused on one of the key Greek civic texts for this discussion, *IG XIV.502* (ISic001323).

¹¹¹ KORHONEN 2017b, reprising more detailed study such as KORHONEN 2011 and in TRIBULATO 2012; cf. the overview of the relationship between Greek and Latin in CAPANO 2019, and BUCCI 2018 on Greek funerary formulae in this context.

¹¹² KORHONEN, SORACI 2019 (note the improved reading of *IG XIV.367* (ISic001190)); cf. BITTO, CALIRI 2018 for texts of this period on Lipari; and see further on this theme PRAG 2024.

¹¹³ The text is *IG XIV.297 = CIL X.7296* (ISic000470). See DE SIMONE 2017; CASTELLI 2018; JAMES, ARBABZADAH 2018; CONSANI 2021.

¹¹⁴ GIGLIO, DE SIMONE 2019; BRUGNONE 2021b; POCSETTI 2021.

¹¹⁵ On Hellenistic honorifics in Sicily see also DIMARTINO 2019 and PRAG 2018a.

monumentalisation noted by others). While the rapid increase in honorific statues at the start of the Imperial period is hardly unexpected and in line with other trends, Henzel highlights also the persistence of the practice in many parts of the island well into Late Antiquity, in contrast to many other parts of the Empire – something which Henzel attributes in part at least to the island’s relationship to North Africa. The focus on an object category in its entirety, of which inscribed examples form only a part, and on a practice within which epigraphic evidence requires considerable contextualisation, is very welcome (funerary monuments could be similarly so treated).

The Greek epigraphy of Sicily therefore continues not only to grow richer as a body of material, but the approaches to that material likewise grow increasingly rich and diverse. More synthetic studies of the island’s epigraphic culture, whether specifically Greek or cross-linguistic, remain few.¹¹⁶ This is no doubt a function both of the lack of an up-to-date and accessible corpus, and of the tendency still to treat the epigraphic material one language at a time, which in Sicily’s case will almost always produce an incomplete picture. Inevitably, I offer the hope that with the *I.Sicily* project we may soon be able to move beyond those particular obstacles.¹¹⁷ But with or without it, the increasing focus on the material and linguistic context of the inscriptions, whether monumental or private, and on honorific, funerary, or ‘magical’ texts (*defixiones*, etc.) offers real promise. We can share the cautious optimism of John Davies, in reviewing recent work on civic sub-divisions in Magna Graecia and Sicily, that both the quantity of material and the quality of the work being done upon it reflects a very different world from when these surveys first began. ‘Micro-epigrafia’ may be flourishing, but it is laying the foundations for exciting new macro-history.¹¹⁸

¹¹⁶ In this period, see PRAG 2018b on Hellenistic epigraphy in Sicily (and 2018c on the specific case of Agrigentine epigraphy).

¹¹⁷ At the time of writing, a new and more powerful search interface for *I.Sicily* is also under development.

¹¹⁸ DAVIES 2018 (*passim*, but at p.130 for ‘micro-epigrafia’).

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